

Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth / Kultūras plaisas mazināšana: lauku ģimeņu stratēģijas jauniešu digitālā kultūras patēriņa prakšu veidošanā

Version 1

Description

The purpose of the data management plan for the project "Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth" is to document and preserve the datasets collected during fieldwork with families. The aim of the study is to explore strategies for shaping digital cultural consumption in rural families and to identify effective approaches for promoting high-quality cultural participation among young people in the digital environment. The research design is based on digital ethnography, combining the researcher's engagement with the family and the family's own self-directed data collection in the digital environment through a mobile ethnography app. The datasets include five types of data: 1) participants' self-assessment questionnaires; 2) interview and focus group transcripts; 3) mobile ethnography data; 4) contextual assessment data, including the evaluation of the family's material objects, the cultural opportunities available in their place of residence, and cultural activities carried out to date; and 5) the researcher's fieldwork notes.

Funder

European Regional

Grant

Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral

Development Fund (ERDF) funding; Latvia's State budget funding; Latvian Academy of Culture funding

Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027

Researchers

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth / Kultūras plaisas mazināšana: lauku ģimeņu stratēģijas jauniešu digitālā kultūras patēriņa prakšu veidošanā

Description:

The purpose of the data management plan for the project "Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth" is to document and preserve the datasets collected during fieldwork with families. The aim of the study is to explore strategies for shaping digital cultural consumption in rural families and to identify effective approaches for promoting high-quality cultural participation among young people in the digital environment. The research design is based on digital ethnography, combining the researcher's engagement with the family and the family's own self-directed data collection in the digital environment through a mobile ethnography app. The datasets include five types of data: 1) participants' self-assessment questionnaires; 2) interview and focus group transcripts; 3) mobile ethnography data; 4) contextual assessment data, including the evaluation of the family's material objects, the cultural opportunities available in their place of residence, and cultural activities carried out to date; and 5) the researcher's fieldwork notes.

Researchers:

Organizations:

Latvian Academy of Culture

Contact: Vinogradova Līga (liga.vinogradova@lka.edu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) funding; Latvia's State budget funding; Latvian Academy of Culture funding

Grants: Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027

Data Management Plan | Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth / Kultūras plaisas mazināšana: lauku ģimeņu stratēģijas jauniešu digitālā kultūras patēriņa prakšu veidošanā LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 07/04/2026

Project: Research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/033 "Bridging the Cultural Divide: Strategies for Rural Families to Curate Digital Cultural Consumption for Youth".

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Interview files with experts

The study will collect qualitative data in the form of in-depth interviews with experts in the cultural field about the digital cultural consumption of children and young people.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The study will collect qualitative data in the form of in-depth interviews with experts in the cultural field about children's and young people's digital cultural consumption, in order to provide contextual information on the situation of children's and young people's cultural consumption in Latvia, including digital cultural consumption.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

6

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Currently, there are no available data on the context of children's and young people's cultural consumption in Latvia.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and education professionals.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Research data created within the project (transcriptions) from interviews with experts will, after anonymisation, be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Text reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Research data created within the project (transcriptions) from interviews with experts will, after anonymisation, be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture - decision Nr. 1.18-1/1. (26.03.2026).

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova. The cost of the Dedoose data analysis software is EUR 17 per month (for each month in which it is used). Interview transcriptions are carried out by research assistants for remuneration.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The interviews will be conducted by the researcher, the transcriptions will be prepared by the research assistant, and the data analysis will be carried out by the researcher.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Institutional cloud server

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project and the research assistant. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Family focus group and interview files

Within the family ethnography, qualitative data will be collected to investigate families' digital cultural consumption strategies. Fieldwork with families will include studying the family as a whole through focus group discussions and individual family members through in-depth interviews. The focus groups will be supplemented with creative elements and will therefore include photographs of creative works produced by the family, which will help stimulate conversation, especially with children and young people.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Within the family ethnography, qualitative data will be collected to investigate families' digital cultural consumption strategies. Fieldwork with families will include studying the family as a whole through focus group discussions and individual family members through in-depth interviews. The focus groups will be supplemented with creative elements and will therefore include photographs of creative works produced by the family, which will help stimulate conversation, especially with children and young people.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no available data on families' cultural consumption in Latvia.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and education professionals.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

cultural consumption, digital cultural consumption, cultural consumption of children and young people, family cultural consumption, family digital practices, reproduction of cultural capital

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transcriptions with family members will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children. The photographs included in the transcriptions will be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Text reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Transcriptions with family members will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children. The photographs included in the transcriptions will be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture - decision xxxxx.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova. The cost of the Dedoose data analysis software is EUR 17 per month (for each month in which it is used). Interview transcriptions are carried out by research assistants for remuneration.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The interviews will be conducted by the researcher, the transcriptions will be prepared by the research assistant, and the data analysis will be carried out by the researcher.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project and the research assistant. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own.

Family members (including children) will be asked to sign a consent form for participation in the study, which also includes consent 1) for the publication/non-publication of the data in an open archive; 2) for the anonymity of the data provided; 4) for the recording of interviews; 3) for the participation of minors in the study (signed only by parents).

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own. Family members (including children) will be asked to sign a consent form for participation in the study, which also includes consent 1) for the publication/non-publication of the data in an open archive; 2) for the anonymity of the data provided; 4) for the recording of interviews; 3) for the participation of minors in the study (signed only by parents). The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project and the research assistant. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

Family self-assessment questionnaires

The dataset will include data submitted by family members in the form of self-assessment questionnaires. These will be collected before and during fieldwork. The self-assessment questionnaires will include information on: a) the socio-demographic information of family members; b) the overall and individual previous cultural consumption assessment of the family and each member; c) the digital content consumption of family members over one month.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Family self-assessment questionnaires

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These data are specific and descriptive for the needs of the particular study in order to explore families.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Family self-assessment questionnaires containing (A) socio-demographic information about family members will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity, as they include personal data, including data about children. Self-assessment questionnaires containing (B) the overall and individual previous cultural consumption assessment of the family and each member, and (C) the digital content consumption of family members over one month, will be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Text reader and XLS and CSV file reader.

SPSS Statistics

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Family self-assessment questionnaires containing (A) socio-demographic information about family members will not be published in open access due to

their sensitivity, as they include personal data, including data about children. Self-assessment questionnaires containing (B) the overall and individual previous cultural consumption assessment of the family and each member, and (C) the digital content consumption of family members over one month, will be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture - decision xxxxx.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova. For data collection, a survey platform (Google Forms or similar) may be used; this is free of charge. Data analysis may use SPSS Statistics, which costs EUR 220 for two years.

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The data will be collected and the data analysis will be carried out by the researcher.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Pseudonymization

The collected self-assessment questionnaires on (A) the socio-demographic information of family members contain sensitive personal data, including data

about minor children. The self-assessment questionnaires on (B) the overall and individual previous cultural consumption assessment of the family and each member, and (C) the digital content consumption of family members over one month, are not sensitive, as they contain a list of activities and their duration without indicating personal data. To describe them, anonymisation has been carried out.

Mobile ethnography data on families

The dataset will include data from the Indeemo mobile ethnography application. Over the course of one month, the family will provide information about their everyday practices in the form of text, photos, videos, and self-assessments.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Family self-assessment questionnaires

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Other

Mobile ethnography notes (inc. text, video and photo)

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- JPG
- Others

MP4

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no available data on families' cultural consumption in Latvia.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Family mobile ethnography notes (including photographs and videos) will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

XLS file reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Family mobile ethnography notes (including photographs and videos) will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the

family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova. For data collection, the paid platform Indemo may be used. The cost of the Dedoose data analysis software is EUR 17 per month (for each month in which it is used).

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The data will be collected and the data analysis will be carried out by the researcher.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Institutional cloud server

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available

only to the researcher involved in the project. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own. Family members (including children) will be asked to sign a consent form for participation in the study, which also includes consent 1) for the publication/non-publication of the data in an open archive; 2) for the anonymity of the data provided; 4) for the recording of interviews; 3) for the participation of minors in the study (signed only by parents).

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own. The data will be pseudonymised, and the analysis will be conducted using pseudonymised data.

Researcher's fieldwork notes

Within the family ethnography, qualitative data will be collected to investigate families' digital cultural consumption strategies. Fieldwork will include observing families at home and at cultural events, as well as interviews and focus groups with their members. During this process, researcher notes will be taken and used in data analysis to assess the relationships among family members.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Within the family ethnography, qualitative data will be collected to investigate families' digital cultural consumption strategies. Fieldwork will include observing families at home and at cultural events, as well as interviews and focus groups with their members. During this process, researcher notes will be taken and used in data analysis to assess the relationships among family members.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These are unique fieldwork notes made by the researcher.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers, especially interested in methodology.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Ethnographic notes will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Text reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Ethnographic notes will not be published in open access due to their sensitivity - they include data about the family's home, everyday life, and daily routine, including information about minor children.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The field notes will be compiled by the researcher conducting the ethnographic study.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Institutional cloud server,

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Pseudonymization

The collected data are sensitive because they include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors. The collected data contain information about the family's home, daily routine, and the material assets they own. Family members (including children) who will be observed will be asked to sign a consent form for participation in the study, which also includes consent 1) for the publication/non-publication of the data in an open archive; 2) for the anonymity of the data provided; 4) for the recording of interviews; 3) for the participation of minors in the study (signed only by parents). The collected data will be pseudonymised before the analysis is carried out. The pseudonym key file

will be stored by the researcher in the institutional cloud storage and deleted after the end of the project.

Summary of contextual information on families' opportunities for cultural consumption

Within the study, contextual data will be collected on families' opportunities for cultural consumption: (A) on the material cultural assets owned by the family and (B) on the offer of cultural activities available in their place of residence.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Within the study, contextual data will be collected on families' opportunities for cultural consumption: (A) on the material cultural assets owned by the family and (B) on the offer of cultural activities available in their place of residence. Both will be collected by the researcher.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Coded textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The data provide specific contextual information about the families under study.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers, cultural sector workers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Tabular data on (A) the material assets owned by the family will, after anonymisation, be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this. (B) Data on the cultural offer available in the place of residence will, after anonymisation (deleting information that would allow a specific municipality and events in it to be identified), be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for the long-term preservation and publication of research data in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

XLS file reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Tabular data on (A) the material assets owned by the family will, after anonymisation, be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged and the research participant has consented to this. (B) Data on the cultural offer available in the place of residence will, after anonymisation (deleting information that would allow a specific

municipality and events in it to be identified), be published in open access and may be used by third parties, provided the source of the data is acknowledged.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Permission to conduct the study has been obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Paid work in data collection, processing, and analysis is carried out by the project implementer Līga Vinogradova.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līga Vinogradova

The data will be collected and the data analysis will be carried out by the researcher.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Any costs will be covered through the internal resources of the Latvian Academy of Culture.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Institutional cloud server

The data will be stored on the institutional cloud server, which provides various security measures such as version control and access control. Access is available only to the researcher involved in the project. The project implementer, Līga Vinogradova, is responsible for data management and the datasets.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Pseudonymization

The collected data on (A) the family's material cultural assets are sensitive because they may include personal data about the family, its individual members, including minors, the material assets they own, and may allow identification of the place of residence. Before publication, the data will be anonymised.

(A) Family members (including children) who will be observed will be asked to sign a consent form for participation in the study, which also includes consent 1) for the publication/non-publication of the data in an open archive; 2) for the anonymity of the data provided; 4) for the recording of interviews; 3) for the participation of

minors in the study (signed only by parents).

Powered by

